

Quality of Life in Families of Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Autism Spectrum Disorder is a complex developmental disability manifested by problems with social communication and interaction, and restrictive and repetitive behaviours of interests. The prevalence of this condition is rapidly growing globally as well as in our Country. Disabilities in children cause not only financial burden, but also leads to incomplete state of well being in physical, social, psychological and environmental domains.

Objective: To evaluate the Quality of Life in Parents of children with Autism as compared to a control group (parents of Neurotypical children).

Study Design: Case Control Study.

Study Population: Study group- Children diagnosed with Autism according to CARS in a Training Centre. Control Group- Children of similar age attending a school in the same Socio demographic setting.

Sample Size: 40 parents in both the Groups.

Sampling Method: Convenient Purposive Sampling.

Study Tool: Quality of Life was assessed by WHO QOL -BREF Questionnaire.

Results: One way ANOVA and Post Hoc tests were used to identify the significant difference of Quality of Life Scores. Parents of children with Autism showed lower QoL as compared to Parents with healthy children (p <0.001). Out of the 4 domains, social and environmental domains were more significantly affected.

Conclusion: Parents of autistic children have significantly impaired Quality of life in all 4 domains (physical, social, psychological and environmental) as measured by WHO QOL- BREF Questionnaire. These findings will help the health care professionals to develop appropriate support Groups and psycho social intervention Programs for the families.

Keywords: Autism Spectrum Disorder, WHO QoL BREF Questionnaire, physical, social, psychological, environmental.

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Introduction

Neurodevelopmental disorders are developmental deficiencies that emerge during the developmental process, most frequently during the preschool period, and characterized by impairment in personal, social, academic, and occupational functionality. Autism Spectrum Disorder is a complex developmental disability manifested by problems with social communication and interactions, and restrictive and repetitive behaviours of interests [1]. It is one of the most common developmental disorders, affecting persons of all ethnic and socio-economic backgrounds [2]. Prevalence of this condition is rapidly growing, globally, as well as in India. Current estimates suggest that in the United States the prevalence of ASD is 20 in every 1000 school-aged children [3]. A recent surge in the number of children identified with ASD has raised concern regarding the burden on parents and caregivers of

children with ASD. In particular, emphasis has fallen on QOL of caregivers.

The World Health Organisation defines QOL as an 'individual's' perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns' [4]. There are four main domains of Quality of Life. These include social relations, relationships with one's setting (environmental health), psychological state and physical well-being. It is thus subjective and culturally governed; definitions may vary, moreover, depending on sociocultural contexts [5]. Previous studies have reported lower QOL in parents of children with ASD in Italy [6], Taiwan [7], as well as Japan [8]. The impact of caring for a child with ASD on parents may be affected by previously reported factors such as stress, coping mechanisms, social support and employment [9].

Studies of QOL have, to date, largely been reported from

western and well-resourced countries. There is a gap in research aimed at measuring the impact of raising children with ASD on parents in resource-limited settings and in India. Many cultural, economic, and educational factors which are highly prevalent in this setting, may independently or cumulatively affect the QOL of caregivers living in India [10]. These factors include poverty, low level of education, material deprivation, poor access to jobs and services, mental and physical ill health. In developing countries, low and middle class income families caring for children with ASD frequently struggle to access professional support services that provide specialist ASD diagnostic, therapeutic and educational services [11,12,13,14]. This, together with other listed factors, results in parents of children with ASD being at high risk of having low QOL.

Objectives:

1. To evaluate the physical health, psychological health, social relationships and environment health of caregivers of children with Autism.
2. To compare the physical health, psychological health, social relationships and environment health of caregivers of children with Autism with caregivers of Neurotypical children.

Methodology:

- Study Design: Case Control Study
- Study Setting:
 - LOCATION: The cases were selected from a Therapy Centre located in Patna, Bihar. The Controls were selected from a Primary School of the same locality
 - Time Period: May 2023 to March, 2024.

Study Population

Study group: Parents of children diagnosed with Autism according to DSM V criteria and CARS 2 in a Training Centre.

Control Group: Parents of children of similar age attending a school in the same Socio demographic setting.

Inclusion Criteria:

Study Group

- The children visiting the Training Centre in Patna, Bihar
- Age Group of 3-6 years
- Children who have been diagnosed as Autism Spectrum Disorder based on CARS 2 or DSM V criteria, by a certified professional

- Whose parents are willing to participate in the study

➤ Control Group:

- The children attending primary school in the same area
- Children belonging to 3-6 years of age
- Whose parents give consent for participation

Exclusion Criteria:

➤ Study Group

- Children with diagnosis other than ASD (Down's syndrome, ADHD,)
- Children with Cerebral Palsy
- Children with Genetic Syndromes
- Children less than 3 years and more than 6 years
- Children accompanied by caregivers other than parents
- If parents do not consent for participation

Control Group

- Children less than 3 years and more than 6 years
- Children accompanied by caregivers other than parents
- If parents do not consent for participation

➤ **Sample Size:** 40 children in both the groups.

➤ **Sampling Method:** Convenient Purposive Sampling.

➤ **Data Collection:** Cases and Controls were selected based on the above criteria. After taking an informed consent and explaining the purpose of study in the local language, a questionnaire was given to them and each question was explained to them. Socio Demographic pattern of parents were recorded. The WHO QOL BREF questionnaire was given to the parents to fill. Completed forms were selected for analysis.

➤ **Study Tools:** The WHOQOL-BREF measure is a shortened version of the WHOQOL-100 which is an international cross-culturally validated measure that evaluates the individual's perceptions in the context of their culture. The WHOQOL-BREF contains 26 items developed in an attempt to provide a measurement of QOL. This instrument includes four main domains; physical, psychological, social and environmental health. The scores rated from 1 to 5, with higher scores denoting higher QOL. Standardised total scores

(percentages) for the QOL scale will be used in this study. The questionnaire was made available in English/Hindi.

- **Data Analysis:** Tests of associations between pairs of nominal variable were conducted using Fisher's exact test, whereas tests of association between continuous variables and categories were conducted using the Kruskal–Wallis test. The data will be analysed using SPSS Software (ver. 20) and Epi info Software.

Ethical Considerations: Necessary approval will be taken from the ethical committee before starting the study. The patients included in the study will not undergo experimental trial of any drug or procedure. All procedures performed in present study involving human participants will be in

accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional Ethics committee.

1. The proposed work will be assessed by Patna Medical College and Hospital Ethics Committee on Human Research.
2. Participant Information Sheet (PIS) will be shared with each participant and informed consent (ICF) will be taken from the participants.
3. Privacy and confidentiality of study participants will be assured.

Observation

Table 1: Demographical Data of The Study Group and Control Group

	Study Group (N=40)	Control Group (N=40)
Father/Mother	12/28 (30%/70%)	14/26 (35%/65%)
Age	36.2± 11.8	38± 12.6
Family Type		
Nuclear Family	24(60%)	21 (52.5%)
Joint Family	16 (40%)	19 (47.5%)
Socio Economic Status		
Upper Class	05 (12.5%)	02 (5%)
Middle Class	34 (85%)	35 (87.5%)
Lower Class	01 (2.5%)	03 (7.5%)
Children's Details		
Boys/Girls	32/08	22/18
Age	5.8±3.25	5.5± 3.25

Table 2: Comparison of WHO BREF QoL between the Study and Control Group

QOL Group	Study Group	Control Group	Significance P Value
Physical Health	68.78 ± 8.44	72.83± 3.93	<0.0001
Psychological Health	66.5± 10.67	78.69±5.98	<0.0001
Social Relationship	52.41± 8.78	95.27 ± 6.85	<0.0001
Environment	66.74± 12.94	94.77± 6.29	<0.0001

Discussion:

The results of our study demonstrate that, the QOL of the parents of children with ASD is significantly lower than the QOL of parents of Neurotypical children from the same community. These findings are consistent with the previous studies that found poorer level of QOL among parents caring of children with ASD as compared with general population in other contexts [15-18,20].

Our study demonstrated significant reduction in QOL across all domains (physical, psychological, social and environmental health) in the parents caring of ASD children. This finding is consistent with that of the South African study [19], which may reflect some similarities between South Africa and India. In particular, general socio-economic, health and economic difficulties, including limited services that cater to those children with ASD and

their caregivers may be common across both environments.

The primary objective of the study was to investigate the differences in QOL between the parents of children with ASD and typically developing children. The study results indicated that the parents of children with ASD had significantly lower scores than parents of typically developing children in all the domains of WHOQOL BREF. Given overall QOL, parents of children with ASD reported poor QOL compared to parents of typically developing children. These findings were in similar lines to the previous studies reporting poor QOL in families of children with ASD (Alhazmi et al. 2018, Calonge-Torres et al. 2017, Dey et al., 2019, Musetti et al. 2021). QOL is a wide concept subjective to an individual's physical-psychological health, level of independence, social ties, personal views, and

relation ship to conspicuous features of their surroundings in a complex way (Kuhlthau et al. 2014). As the results of the present study indicated that all of these domains were affected, parents of children with ASD showed overall poorer QOL. Parents of children with ASD indicated significantly poor overall health and physical health compared to parents of typically developing children. [21]

Children with ASD need continuous care, which can be taxing physically as well as psychologically for the parents. Greater levels of stress, sleep deprivation, and also tiredness, faced by the parents can be attributed to their lower mental and physical performance of parents (Catalano et al. 2018). Earlier studies have reported that the QOL was consistently worse especially in the physical domain than in the psychological health (Musetti et al. 2021). Though the exact reasons were unknown, the study reckoned the outcome of raising children with special needs as one of the likely reasons for the consistent worsening of QOL in parents having children with special needs (Deyet al. 2019). Previous studies also have indicated that when compared to controls, the families having a child with ASD have often reported poor overall and physical health (Calonge-Torres et al. 2017, Shu 2009, Tung et al. 2014). [22]

The results of the study also indicated that self-rated psychological health was poorer than physical health and was the second-highest affected domain. Although poor psychological health is often linked to increased stress levels in parents raising children with ASD, it has also been related to parental sentiments of loneliness (Alenazi et al. 2020, Shu 2009, Tung et al. 2014). Additionally, in the Indian scenario, the concerns about the child's future might have led to grief, emotions of self-blame, guilt, and social humiliation and may negatively impact the psychological health of the parents (Ahmed et al. 2019, Grace et al. 2017, [23]

Perumal et al. 2014). Though it is common to find psychological well being affected in parents of children with ASD; given the Indian context, they often blame themselves and are hesitant to seek professional treatment for their psychological issues (Grace et al., 2017). [24]

Further, myths, mis diagnosis, and misunderstandings about ASD, its causes, lack of trustworthy information, cultural and communal obstacles, and lack of knowledge and acceptance by the community increases the stress level in parents in a multicultural country like India and in turn negatively affects the QOL of parents of children with ASD (Ahmed et al., 2019, Grace et al., 2017). This prejudice in Indian society plays a crucial role in determining the QOL. So, parents' psychological discomfort and coping strategies must be addressed

as part of a comprehensive intervention for children with ASD (Kuhlthau et al. 2014, Renford et al. 2020). It was also observed that the parents of children with ASD reported least scores in the domain of social relationships which was also significantly low compared to parents of typically developing children. Notably, ASD has an influence on the child's connection with his or her parents, as well as the family's interaction with the community (Alhazmi et al. 2018). Further, the high caregiving responsibilities might limit parental opportunities to dedicate time outside the home and socialize. It has also been reported that stigmatization, more care giving obligations, and greater financial demands for taking care children with ASD may limit parents' cap ability to socialize and bring positive changes to their environment (Shu 2009). [25]

Overall, follow-up services and continued support for parents of children with ASD is an essential components to help parents adapt and meet their needs and the children's needs in India. The available literature and the results of the present study suggest that parents of children with ASD present with considerable challenges adversely affecting their QOL (Ahmed et al. 2019, Grace et al. 2017). Therefore, support groups are vital for parents, siblings, and other family members of children with ASD to obtain proper informational and emotional support which are critical to their well-being.

Different types of support groups available for parents of children with ASD include peer-led support groups that are led by parents of children with ASD; professionally-led support groups that are directed by professionals such as psychologists, and special educators. As these types of support groups and their services are well acknowledged by the parents and family members of children with ASD, government and non-government organizations have established various ASD support groups across the world. With increased understanding of the condition, acceptance and awareness about the facilities available for children with ASD among developed countries like the United States (Khanna et al. 2011), Australia (Eapen et al. 2014), and Europe (Ikeda et al. 2014), the accessibility to support groups are also relatively high in these countries. However, there is an extensive need to increase the number of support groups and their role in meeting various QOL needs in parents of children with ASD in many developing countries like India.

Scientific Merits of the Study:

- Autism spectrum disorder is not uncommon in India, unfortunately, very few studies are only done on measuring the quality of life of families of children with autism spectrum

disorder in India.

- This shall assist in identifying the effectiveness of services available in India and also it would give us guidelines for managing the stress related issues in the family.

Limitations Of the Study:

- Small sample size and sample collected from a single locality
- The findings are derived based on parental reports and no direct observation of the quality of family life was conducted.

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